
TYPES OF DIPLOMATIC CORRESPONDING IN UZBEK AND FRENCH, AND THEIR STYLISTIC CHARACTERIZATION

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Abstract.

This article analyzes the types of diplomatic text and the research carried out by scientists on them. Diplomatic texts are classified and justified by examples.

Keywords.

diplomatic text, diplomatic discourse, official style, diplomatic negotiations, style of diplomatic documents

The language and style of diplomatic documents have been studied extensively, and H.Wildner's book "The Technique of Diplomacy" deserves special attention in this area. German scientist H.Wildner noted that "the diplomatic style is, first of all, simplicity and should be distinguished by its accuracy; by this, not the simplicity of the vocabulary method is meant, but the form of simplicity, which in these conditions knows how to choose the only word suitable for each subject. An unusual way of expression, as well as verbosity, leads to a lack of simplicity"²⁴.

Several studies have been carried out on the determination of diplomatic approach, position in the system of formal-business functional style, including M.N. Kojina's work, which is devoted to the study of functional styles in linguistics. Functional speech style is a specific type of socially conscious speech that corresponds to a specific sphere of social activity and the form of consciousness, which is a specific form of speech (structure) determined by the tasks of communication in the relevant field, having its own norms for the selection and combination of linguistic units in this area. From this definition it follows that the functional style of language is characterized by more extralinguistic features.

M.P.Brandes defines the style in his scientific work "Text Stylistics" as follows: "the style not only represents the technology of spiritual production of a certain

²⁴ Wildner H. Die Technik der Diplomatie. Wien, Springer – Verlag, 1959.

type in a particular historical situation, but also expresses the specifics and specificity of any human activity, including communication and speech, as well as its result”²⁵. Functional style is a special reality in which a certain system of forms and stereotypes, features find expression. Such a system, in turn, is divided into several subsystems, one of which is a small system that reflects the method of text content. Distinctive features of the style: purposefulness, consistency and informational character²⁶.

L.K.Graudina defines the official style as follows: “official style -state body, organization and management, organization and individual -formal style always serves as a guide on entrepreneurship, economics, trade, law and diplomacy”²⁷. Language style is understood as a set of lexical, grammatical and phonetic means of expressing the stylistic technique of a particular area.

In order to determine the features of the diplomatic front style, as well as other styles, it is necessary to consider the material at the text level. Within the framework of the study of Text Linguistics, we will focus on the concept of “text type”: Texttyp, Textsorte, Textklasse, Textgruppe, Textart. In linguistics, there is no absolutely accurate translation of this phenomenon. Linguists use the working term “text type” as a fundamental. According to V.E.Chernyavskaya’s definition, “text type is a “systematic prototype” that is a model, sample, structure scheme, and the perception of similar texts (Textbildungsmuster, Textschemata) or a prototype for the construction of other texts of a certain category, but with a different content and structure”²⁸. Each type of text has its own characteristics. When combining texts into a specific text group, their properties are taken into account. In V.E. Chernyavskaya’s works, the concept of the type of text denotes an effective model developed culturally and historically, an example of a textual structure that determines the functional and structural features (“text copies”) of certain texts with different thematic content. Any example of text exists as an implementation of the appropriate type of text. The scientist offers two ways to typologize “text examples”: “top-down path” (from general parameters to the implementation of specific text) and “bottom-up path” from real texts to their unification. The second method of typologizing the types of “diplomatic texts” is followed.

²⁵ *Брандес*, М.П. Стилистика текста. Теоретический курс = Учебник / *Брандес* М. П. – Москва : Прогресс-Традиция, **2004**. – 208. - С.140-141.

²⁶ Ёша манба.

²⁷ *Граудина* Л.К., Ширяев Е.Н. Культура русской речи и эффективность общения. ... Монография. — Белгород: Изд-во Белгородского гос. ун-та, **1999**.-С. 216-218

²⁸ Чернявская В.Е. Лингвистика текста. Полиодовость. Интертекстуальность, Интердискурсивность. - М.: URSS, 2009. - 245 С. –С.57-58.

Many scientists believe that on the basis of the concept of the type of text, textsorts in a particular field of communication can be distinguished. However, there is no connection between Uzbek, Russian and Western linguists about the method of classification of types of text. According to V.E.Chernyavskaya a copy of the text is, a particular work of text exists in the linguistic system as a representative of the corresponding type of text and should be considered in this way. N.S. Valgina notes that typologization of texts (criteria for dividing texts into specific types), despite its versatility, occurs on the basis of highlighting the main features of the text: informational, functional, structural-semiotic and communicative²⁹.

In our opinion, the most understandable and broad interpretation of the term “type of text”, K.A.Filippov quoted by: in modern linguistics, the term “text type” is used to describe stable text forms and accurately implement this form in speech. “In this case, the type of text is understood as a form of text in which the communicative intention of the speaker is realized and built according to certain rules and norms” that is, each text has its own characteristics (textual characteristics) inherent in this type of communication, along with its specificity, morphological, stylistic, syntactic and other characteristics. The classification of text typologies is not one-sided. Thus, the author lists the main textual classifications of Russian and foreign linguists . The typology of texts is considered taking into account linguistic and extralinguistic factors.

Types of text ranges by different scientists depending on the text belonging to a particular category, the functionality of the text, as well as other characteristics. Barbara Zandig divides texts into eighteen classes based on extralinguistic attributions: letter, interview, advertising, etc³⁰. E.Grosse identifies eight classes of text types based on the function performed by the text ³¹. Depending on this or that classification, the texts of the diplomatic sphere can apply to different types of texts.

M. P. Brandes defines the type of text as follows: “within certain types of texts, there is a further differentiation of texts based on the more specific purpose of

29 Валгина Н.С. Розенталь Д.Э. Фомина М.И. Современный русский язык: Учебник / Под редакцией Н.С. Валгиной. - 6-е изд., перераб. и доп. Москва: Логос, 2002.

350 с. –С 113

30 Güllich, Raible. Text-grammars, text-theory and the theory of literature. 1970 : 196 p.

31 Heinemann W, Viehweger D. Textlinguistik. Jul 22, 2011 - Language Arts & Disciplines - 310 pages. 1991 : 138-139).

objectified speech in speech genres” 32. For Example, E.G. Rizel understands the type of text as a class of certain written and oral texts with the same functional and situational characteristics, if not the same, at least with similar linguistic characteristics³³. The type of text is usually defined in communicative situations based on characteristics. In the field of diplomacy, as in other official business-style texts, as a result of communication activities, certain types of diplomatic texts have their own characteristics and structure. The diplomatic document, which is considered an element of diplomatic speech, contains the results of diplomatic activity and text elements that send the recipient to other texts of diplomatic corresponding.

Types of texts in the diplomatic sphere can be distinguished depending on the types of activities:

1. Texts of diplomatic correspondence documents;
2. Texts as a result of negotiations;
3. Texts published in the media and on the official website of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs;
4. Contract texts.

In the above-mentioned L.G.Faravonova’s works, the typology of texts from a linguistic-stylistic point of view is interesting.

The author distinguishes the styles of text types according to the hierarchy of the system of functional styles of formal work. L.G. Farafonova clearly distinguishes such concepts as “text type”, “text type style “ and “text subtype style”. It would seem that the diplomatic front style is considered as a structural element of the official style of work, and diplomatic documents, according to the scientist, can be divided into groups of text types. The types of text belong to the written form of diplomatic activity (documents) and cover:

- Internal documents;
- Documents related to the appointment and recall of diplomatic representatives (credentials, notes);
- Documents for publication in the press or statement of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs (statement of official representatives of foreign ministries, press releases);
- Documents related to ratification, accession, denunciation;

³²Брандес, М.П. Стилистика текста. Теоретический курс = Учебник / Брандес М. П. – Москва : Прогресс-Традиция, 2004. –С. 10.

³³Ризель Э. Г. Стилистика немецкого языка. -Москва: Высшая школа, 1975. -316 с. –С.13.

- Documents of diplomatic correspondence;
- Documents resulting from negotiations;

The style of diplomatic texts is characterized by generality, informativeness, objectivity, logical presentation, semantic clarity and accuracy, adherence to diplomatic ethics. The above features are reflected in the use of well-established speech constructions, clichés, diplomatic terms, defined rules and expressions. The features of the official style of work are reflected in the texts of diplomatic activity in the form of specific language tools that form a language system of different levels: lexical-semantic, stylistic, morphological and syntactic, such as. The diplomatic text initially manifests itself in a special choice of language tools in the process of preparing documents that are “embedded” in the diplomatic front style, in the framework of strict adherence to the rules of the diplomatic protocol and their translation into a foreign language.